

EXPERIMENTAL RESEARCH OF FORMING-TORSIONING DEVICES WHEN TWISTING YARN IN A PNEUMOMECHANICAL METHOD OF SPINNING

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Abstract. *The paper presents the results of a study of the dynamics of the process of torsion of yarn of pneumomechanical spinning in the presence of false torsion, dynamic mathematical models of the process of torsion of yarn of pneumomechanical spinning in the presence of false torsion in unsteady modes of starting and stopping the forming-twisting device are constructed. By now, the question of yarn twisting in a transient mode of operation in rotor spinning remains unexplored. We have here made an attempt to fill the indicated gap by constructing mathematical models of a forming-twisting device during torsion. In connection with the above-mentioned information, the problem arises to systematize the accumulated information on new methods of forming yarn and constructions of forming and torque devices, to clarify a number of questions of theory and technology, and also to classify methods of forming yarn. The main direction of development of new methods of yarn formation remains the improvement of the high-speed modes of the working organs and, above all, of the forming and turning devices, which raises a number of important problems of both technological and structural nature.*

Keywords: *pneumomechanical spinning; yarn; twist; rated twist; twist direction; torsion process; false torsion; transient mode; start; stop; analytical dependence.*

INTRODUCTION. For the modern textile industry, one of the characteristic trends remains the desire to increase the productivity of technological machines by increasing speed, which causes not only an increase in workloads, but also a sharp increase in energy costs and a decrease in efficiency.

This situation poses the problem of reducing energy costs in rotor spinning, the successful solution of which requires the use of non-traditional approaches to its solution.

In connection with the above, the problem arises of systematizing the accumulated information on new methods of forming yarn and the designs of forming-torsion devices, clarifying a number of issues of theory and technology, as well as classifying methods of forming yarn. The main direction in the development of new methods for forming yarn remains increasing the speed conditions of the working bodies and, first of all, the forming-twisting devices, in connection with which a number of important problems of both a technological and design nature arise. One of the important problems is the sharp increase in power consumption of forming-torsion devices with increasing rotation speed. As shown in [1], the relationship between power consumption and rotational speed of forming and torsion devices is exponential. Since the share of power consumed by forming-twisting devices in air-mechanical spinning machines is currently 70 percent or more, in the context of the modern requirement for comprehensive savings of all resources, and first of all, fuel and energy [2], the relevance of this problem increases.

A well-known feature of rotor spinning yarn, which consists in high twist coefficients compared to ring spinning yarn [1,2], due to the peculiarity of the structure of rotor spinning yarn and the conditions of its formation, greatly aggravates the problem of increasing the power consumed by forming-twisting devices. This, in turn, makes relevant the problem of reducing the twist coefficient of rotor spinning yarn, the solution of which would provide an additional opportunity to achieve an increase in the speed of yarn formation in rotor spinning machines without increasing the rotation speed of the forming-twisting devices with a corresponding reduction in power consumption.

The main objectives of the experimental study of the twisting process in rotor spinning were to determine the average twist of the produced yarn in a steady state of operation, the maximum twist value during the start-up period, and determine the ratio of these two quantities, calculated determination of the value of twist in steady-state operating mode and the maximum value of twist during the start-up period on a computer using the theoretical mathematical models constructed [2,3,4,5,6,8,10], comparison of the experimental value of the maximum twist during the start-up period with the calculated value and on this basis the adoption of a conclusion about the adequacy of the constructed models.

AIMS, OBJECTIVES AND GENERAL RESEARCH METHODOLOGY. The experiments were carried out on machines of the rotor spinning method R-60, which are in operation at "Akhsin" spinning factory and on an experimental stand for rotor spinning, manufactured by the author after conducting experiments to optimize design parameters.

Due to the fact that [6] only for the forming-twisting devices of the R-60 air-spinning machine, mathematical models were built for three sections of yarn according to the technological scheme for two stop periods and three start periods, we end up with 15 mathematical torsion process models [6].

However, on the one hand, the amount of twist in the third section of yarn according to the technological scheme is entirely determined by the amount of twist and the progress of the technological process in the previous, first and second sections of yarn according to the technological scheme, and on the other hand, the changes in yarn twists over time in all sections are unique determined by its changes in previous periods.

Therefore, the adequacy of the mathematical model for the third section of yarn in the third start-up period fully determines the adequacy of the mathematical models for the first and second sections of yarn according to the technological scheme of the machine at all previous periods of start-up, as well as stoppage, since the problem of torsion during start-up was solved based on the solution to the problem of yarn torsion under stopping conditions.

Fig.1. Calculation scheme in the presence of double false torsion.

Table.1.a

Sorting composition and technological indicators of cotton fiber (averaged)

Selected cotton variety	Fiber grade	in %	Modal length	Staple length	Clogging, %
AH-402	I	30	29.4	32.7	2.9
T-3	I	15			
T-3	II	15			
C-47-27	I	20			
T-1	III	15			
Returns		5			
Total		100	29.4	32.7	2.9

All experiments in this work were carried out with the same sorting composition used at the "Akhsin" spinning factory. (table 1 a and b).

The R-60 machine produced yarn with a thickness of 29.4 tex (actually 30.2 tex), and the stand also produced 29.4 tex (actually 30.9 tex).

Table 1.b

Technological indicators of yarn produced on R-60 machines

1.	Design yarn density	29,4
2.	Actual density	30,2
3.	Design twist factor	53,03
4.	Actual twist factor	52,1
5.	Design twist	978 twist/min
6.	Actual twist	948 twist/min
7.	Relative strength	9,8 f/fti

EXPERIMENTAL STUDY OF FORMING-TWISTING DEVICES WHEN TWISTING YARN ON AN R-60 ROTOR SPINNING MACHINE DURING THE START-UP PERIOD.

The torsion of pneumo-mechanical yarn during the start-up period was studied on R-60 machines, which are in operation at the "Akhsin" spinning factory with inventory numbers № 8, 9, 10. The first 20 spinning places on the left side of each machine were allocated for the experiments.

Three launches were carried out, the second and third launches with a duration of operation after launch of 5 minutes, and the first launch with a duration of operation after start of 15 minutes. After the third start-up, they continued to work without interruption: on machine № 8 there were 14 spinning places, on machines № 9 and 10, respectively, 11 and 17 spinning places, for a total of 42 spinning places, the yarn from which was subjected to further research.

In each sample, the twist was determined on three segments produced during start-up and on three segments produced in steady-state operation. It was established above that the maximum value of twist at start occurs at $t_m = 0.83$ sec, and since the movement of the yarn in the forward direction begins at the moment $t_2 = 0.58$ sec, during the time $t_m - t_2 = 0.83 - 0.58 = 0.25$ sec the yarn travels a path equal to $S = v(t_m - t_2) = 0.528 - 0.25 = 0.132$ m.

But during the first start-up period, the yarn moves in the opposite direction and travels a path equal to $1.25 = 1.25 * 3.14 - 0.065 = 0.255$ m, where d_b - the diameter of the outlet shaft. Thus, at the moment of maximum, the yarn section, compared to the start of the start-up, turns out to be shifted towards the chamber by $0.255 - 0.132 = 0.123$ m. If we keep in mind that the length of the second section of yarn is 0.35 m, in the center of the section there will be a point of yarn located at a distance of $(0.350 : 2) - 0.123 = 0.052$ m from the clamping line of the output shaft. Therefore, before starting, marks were applied to the yarn at a distance of 0.05 m from the clamping line by spraying paint and subsequently the amount of twist was determined by pieces of yarn 0.25 m long with a mark in the center.

The results of determining yarn twist are given in table 2 and 3.

Table 2.

Results of determining the maximum twist during start-up on the R-60 machine

N_0	K_m	$(K_m - \bar{K}_m)$	N_0	K_m	$(K_m - \bar{K}_m)^2$	N_0	K_m	$(K_m - \bar{K}_m)^2$
1	323	18,81	9	321	4,41	17	323	16,81
2	316	8,41	10	298	436,81	18	340	334,91
3	322	9,61	11	295	571,21	19	309	98,01
4	322	9,61	12	321	4,41	20	307	141,61
5	345	81,21	13	325	37,21	21	327	65,01
6	315	15,21	14	332	171,61	22	320	1,21
7	316	8,41	15	327	65,01			
8	328	82,81	16	316	8,41			

Table 3.

Results of determination of twist in steady state on the R-60 machine

N_0	K_m	$(K_m - \bar{K}_m)^2$	N_0	K_m	$(K_m - \bar{K}_m)^2$	N_0	K_m	$(K_m - \bar{K}_m)^2$
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
1	230	18,49	11	238	13,69	21	238	13,69
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
2	243	75,69	12	235	0,49	22	237	7,29
3	235	9,49	13	248	187,09	23	212	497,29
4	238	13,69	14	244	94,09	24	243	75,69

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
5	251	278,89	15	235	0,49	25	230	18,49
6	213	453,69	16	240	32,49	26	239	22,09
7	234	0,09	17	213	453,69	27	235	0,49
8	229	28,09	18	227	53,29	28	214	412,09
9	240	32,49	19	239	22,09	29	252	313,29
10	237	7,29	20	217	299,29	30	243	75,69

PROCESSING THE EXPERIMENT RESULTS.

1. Calculating the average values of twists

$$\bar{K}_m = \frac{\sum_1^m K_{m1}}{m} = \frac{\sum_1^{30} K_{m1}}{30} = \frac{9568}{30} = 318,9 \text{ twist/meter}$$

$$\bar{K}_y = \frac{\sum_1^m K_{y1}}{m} = \frac{\sum_1^{30} K_{y1}}{30} = \frac{7029}{30} = 234,3 \text{ twist/meter}$$

Since the measurements were carried out on 0.25 m pieces of yarn, the average value of yarn twist per meter will be:

$$\bar{K}_m = 318,9 = 1275 \text{ twist/meter}$$

$$\bar{K}_y = 234,4 = 937 \text{ twist/meter}$$

2. Calculating the variance of twists using the formula [78]:

$$S^2\{\bar{K}_m\} = \frac{1}{m-1} \sum_1^m (K_{m1} - \bar{K}_m)^2 \quad (1)$$

$$S^2\{\bar{K}_m\} = \frac{1}{30-1} \sum_1^m (K_{m1} - \bar{K}_m)^2 = \frac{3217,9}{30-1} = 110,96$$

$$S^2\{\bar{K}_y\} = \frac{1}{30-1} \sum_1^{30} (K_{y1} - \bar{K}_y)^2 = \frac{3502,7}{29} = 120,77$$

3. Checking the experimental data that stands out sharply using the Smirnov-Grabs criterion, determined by the formula [78]:

$$V_{Re xt} = \frac{|y_{ext} - \bar{y}|}{s\{y\}} \sqrt{\frac{m}{m-1}} \quad (2)$$

We have:

$$V_{Re xt} K_m = \frac{|345 - 318,9|}{\sqrt{110,96}} \sqrt{\frac{30}{30-1}} = 2,51$$

$$V_{Re xt} K_y = \frac{|212 - 234,3|}{\sqrt{120,77}} \sqrt{\frac{30}{30-1}} = 2,06$$

Table value of criterion [78]:

$$V_T[P_D = 0,95, m = 25] = 2,72$$

Thus:

$$V_{Re\ xy}K_m = 2,51 < V_T = 2,72$$

$$V_{Re\ xt}K_y = 2,06 < V_T = 2,72$$

Thus, the tested extreme values of twists cannot be excluded from further consideration. Determining the quadratic irregularities of twists using the formula [78]:

$$C\{y\} = \frac{s\{y\}}{\bar{y}} 100\% \quad (3)$$

We have:

$$C\{K_m\} = \sqrt{\frac{110,96}{318,9}} 100 = 3,30\%$$

$$C\{K_y\} = \sqrt{\frac{120,77}{234,3}} 100 = 4,69\%$$

Determining the relative confidence errors in determining twists using the formula [78]:

$$\delta\{\bar{y}\} = t_{T2}\{P_D\}C\{y\} \frac{1}{\sqrt{m}} \quad (5)$$

We have:

$$\delta\{\bar{K}_y\} = +2,045 \cdot 4,69 \frac{1}{\sqrt{30}} = 1,75\%$$

7. Let us determine the average value of the ratio of the maximum twist at start-up K_m to the twist in steady state K_y - the start-up dynamic coefficient according to the formula

$$k_{\text{э}} = \frac{\bar{K}_m}{K_y} \quad (6)$$

We have:

$$k_{\text{э}} = \frac{318,9}{234,3} = 1,36$$

CONCLUSION. Thus, the maximum twist at start-up exceeds the twist in steady state by 1.36 times.

Fig.2. Graph of dependence of torsion on time

Comparison of the value $k_3 = 1,36$ with the value $k_{\text{э}} = 1,36$ obtained in the previous paragraph shows that the actual value of the ratio coefficient of Maximum twist at start-up to twist in steady state operation exceeds its calculated value by approximately 1.5%, although it should expect the opposite. The analysis showed that this is due to the fact that when constructing mathematical models of forming-twisting devices, the linear speed of the yarn was assumed to be constant, that is $v = \text{const}$, but in fact it increases from zero to value equal to v .

This circumstance causes the actual value of the coefficient to exceed the theoretically calculated one.

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